

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE EFFECTS OF INSTAGRAM AND SNAPCHAT ON THE
HEALTH AND BEAUTY OF THE SMILE AMONG THE SAUDI
POPULATION**

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¹Ibn Sina National College for Medical Studies, Dental department.**Abstract:**

In today's world, most of us have an account on the social media and are influenced by it in some ways. There are many uses of social media in the field of dentistry. The online applications provide a platform to share different contents related to dentistry. There is a growing usage of social media applications especially among the young people all across the world and even among the Saudi population. The main aim of this study is to evaluate the effects of Instagram and Snapchat on the health and beauty of the smiles of the Saudi population. The final questionnaire was distributed online via email to different people in Saudi Arabia. The data that was collected from the questionnaire was analyzed using the computer software SPSS 16. The results of the survey showed that the social media applications like Instagram and Snapchat influences the health and beauty of the smiles of the Saudi Arabia's population. The younger generations of Saudi Arabia have had an increase demand of dentistry services in the past years. The oral awareness has also increased in Saudi Arabia by using these social media applications like Instagram and Snapchat.

Keywords: *Social media, Instagram, Snapchat, Oral health awareness, Celebrity smile, cosmetic dentistry.*

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Please cite this article in press Waad Ahmed AlMazrouie et al., *The Effects Of Instagram And Snapchat On The Health And Beauty Of The Smile Among The Saudi Population.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(02).

INTRODUCTION:

Social media is one such platform that covers a number of websites and online applications that allows the user to create and share their content and participate in social networking [1]. In today's world many people have been influenced by contents from the social media. Social media not only plays an important role in our personal life but it is also important professionally [2]. Dentistry is no exception as it uses it in a professional manner. There are many uses of social media in the field of dentistry. The online applications provide a platform to share different contents related to dentistry [3].

Today there is an increase of views about the new technologies that deals with oral health topics, dental care and cosmetic dentistry in Saudi Arabia [4].

The online applications of the social media has changed the traditional way of spreading knowledge, as it allows anyone with Internet access the opportunity to evaluate as well as to participate in collaborative sharing of ideas.

These online social media applications help the dentist to reach out to the widest possible number of patients at the lowest cost of marketing per patient [5]. When compared to the other forms of marketing and advertising, social media networking requires less efforts and money to achieve great results [6].

RATIONALE BEHIND THIS STUDY:

The main reason behind selecting this topic is to study and evaluate the effects and the influence of social media applications like instagram and snapchat on the health and beauty of the smile among the Saudi population. There is a growing use of social media applications especially among the young people all across the world and even in the Saudi population. Here we want to study that these populations are really influenced by the promotions of oral health care awareness. The carrying of beautiful smiles by various celebrities can cause an urge among the people to change their smiles into a picture perfect smile.

AIM & OBJECTIVES:

The main aim of this study is to evaluate the effects of instagram and snapchat on the health and beauty of

the smiles among the Saudi population. This can be attained by:

- Conducting a survey to determine the effects of instagram and snapchat on the oral health of the Saudi population.
- Identifying the choice of people opting for many cosmetic dentistry procedures by viewing the ads on instagram and snapchat.
- Evaluating the role of these social media applications like instagram and snapchat on the health and beauty of the smile of the Saudi population.

METHODOLOGY:

After reviewing the literature regarding the effects of instagram and snapchat on the health and beauty of the smile of the people, a questionnaire was selected from one of the previous studies and the modification were done in order to meet the requirements of the present study.

The final questionnaire was distributed online via email to different people in Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire consisted of the basic demographic information about the Saudi citizens and also single answer multiple choice type questions related to the effects of social media applications on oral health and the beauty of the smile. This study includes the common citizens residing in Saudi Arabia.

DATA ANALYSIS:

The data that was collected from the questionnaire was analyzed using the computer software SPSS 16. The frequencies and percentages of the responses from the Saudi population using the P value equal to or less than 0.05.

RESULTS:

The questionnaire was distributed to a wide number of citizens in Saudi Arabia. Results from about 373 citizens were collected successfully. Out of all the people that answered the questionnaire, about 62% were females and 38% were males.

Majority of the individuals of about 45% were in the age group of 19-25 years, while 22% were in 26-35 years age group, and about 18% in 36-45 years age group.

Majority of the population had an account on Instagram, of about 92%, and the remaining 8% had no account on any social media applications.

About 84% of the Saudi citizens had an account on snapchat, while the remaining 16% had no account on snapchat.

73% of the Saudi population is interested in watching oral health awareness videos on instagram and snapchat.

About 62% of the Saudi population is interested in following a dentist on snapchat and instagram.

The majority of the citizens of Saudi, of about 79%, were influenced by a celebrity with a beautiful smile.

Around 71% of the participants believe in oral health promotions on Instagram and Snapchat, while 29% doesn't believe in these oral health promotions.

DISCUSSION:

In present time, social media has been so popular that it is not surprising that professional doctors and hospitals and other Healthcare professionals are using the social media and online applications to market, communicate and connect with their patients.

Dentistry has also an increased interest in using

social media accounts to communicate and market to their patients. The results of the survey show that dentists use the social media to promote their services and products. Younger dentists in particular, opt for the social media applications more often than older dentists. Many people, mostly younger generations, use the social media applications like Instagram and

Snapchat to update their knowledge regarding new technologies.

They view the accounts of many celebrities who use new Cosmetic dentistry Technologies in order to get that Picture Perfect smile. When viewing these celebrities' accounts, the younger generations is inspired to get the perfect smile and are attracted to go for these services offered by the dentists.

Hence, social media applications like Instagram and Snapchat influences the health and beauty of the smile of the population of Saudi Arabia. The younger generations of Saudi Arabia have had an increase demand of dentistry services in the past years.

The oral awareness has also increased in Saudi Arabia by using these social media applications like Instagram and Snapchat. People are more educated with regard to the tips and advices from the dentists in their posts and videos on Instagram and Snapchat.

CONCLUSION:

In the 21st century, the internet is being used worldwide and also the social media online applications for a variety of purposes including dentistry. Social media has helped us in expanding our knowledge and helped us learn things that we were not aware of before. They are easy to access for both the dentist as well as the patients. The common people have become familiar with using Instagram and Snapchat to update themselves about the new technologies in dentistry. They follow many dentists to get more information and knowledge about the new technologies in dentistry and also the oral Health Care awareness. People can easily figure out the pros and cons of any technology that is used to enhance their beauty and smile using cosmetic dentistry. The dentist's interpretation and the cosmetic parameters of celebrities through these applications have increased the oral health performance and esthetic demands.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

Compliance with ethical standards

Ethical approval: This research has an Ethical approval for the study of the effects of instagram and snapchat on the health and beauty of the smile among the Saudi population.

Conflict of interest: The authors do not have any commercial associations that might pose or create a conflict of interest with information presented in this communication. No intramural or extramural funding supported any aspect of this work.

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